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Participant Perceptions on Career Fairs: A Comparison of Kudakaf '23 and Kudakaf '25

Kariyer Fuarları Katılımcı Algıları: Kudakaf'23 ve Kudakaf'25 Karşılaştırması

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to reveal the perception of public and private sector institutions/organizations and NGOs within the target group of Regional Career Fairs (RCFs), organized with the motto of "Talent is Everywhere" in Türkiye, through Atatürk University and its students, and Regional Career Fairs and Northeastern Anatolia Career Fairs (KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25). It will also help employers provide feedback to the RCFs, regularly held at the national level since 2019, and contribute to the still-developing national literature based on the KUDAKAF example.

A university hosted the RCFs under the coordination of the Presidency of Turkey and in collaboration with other universities designated by the Presidency within the region. Its objective was to bring together students from RCFs, public and private sector institutions/organizations, and host and partner universities, thus facilitating students' access to job and internship opportunities, regardless of the advantages and disadvantages associated with the regional disparities of the universities where they receive their education. The purposes of this research, designed based on the objectives of RCFs as outlined by the Presidency, were to identify the perceptions and assessments of participating employer representatives towards Atatürk University and its students, RCFs, KUDAKAF '23, and KUDAKAF '25, and to detect if there are differences between the two RCFs. In line with the research objective, employers who participated in KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 completed a Likert-type scale, specially developed for the current study, during the fair days, which provided quantitative data. The study analyzed the collected quantitative data through simple statistical techniques. As a result, the study concluded that participants considered career fairs essential in accessing skilled labor and that the fairs potentially offer substantial employment opportunities to students.

Keywords: Regional Career Fair, Northeastern Anatolia Career Fair, Atatürk University, Perception.

ÖZET

Bu çalışmanın amacı, Bölgesel Kariyer Fuarlarının (BKF) katılımcısı olan kamu ve özel sektör kurum/kuruluşları ile STK'ların Atatürk Üniversitesi ile öğrencilerine ve Bölgesel Kariyer Fuarları ile Kuzeydoğu Anadolu Kariyer Fuarlarına (KUDAKAF'23 ve KUDAKAF'25) ilişkin algısının ortaya konulmasıdır. Bu araştırma ile, ayrıca, ülkemizde 2019 yılından beri düzenli olarak gerçekleştirilen BKF'lere, Kuzeydoğu Anadolu Kariyer Fuarı (KUDAKAF) örneğinden hareketle, işverenler tarafından bir geri dönüş sağlanmakta ve henüz gelişmekte olan ilgili literatüre katkı yapılmaktadır.

BKF'ler Cumhurbaşkanlığı İnsan Kaynakları Ofisi koordinasyonunda bir üniversitenin ev sahipliğinde ve Cumhurbaşkanlığı tarafından belirlenmiş bölgede yer alan diğer üniversitelerin paydaşlığında gerçekleştirilmiştir. BKF'lerin amaçlarından hareketle tasarlanan bu araştırmanın hedefleri de, KUDAKAF'23 ve KUDAKAF'25 örneklerinde katılımcı işveren temsilcilerinin Atatürk Üniversitesi'ne, Atatürk Üniversitesi öğrencilerine, BKF'lere yönelik algı ve değerlendirmelerinin ve bu değerlendirmelerin her iki fuar açısından farklılıklarının ortaya konulmasıdır. Araştırma kapsamında KUDAKAF'23 ve KUDAKAF'25 katılımcısı olan işverenlere fuar günlerinde bu araştırma için geliştirilmiş likert tipi ölçek uygulanarak nicel veri toplanmıştır. Toplanan nicel veri basit istatistikî tekniklerle analiz edilmiştir. Araştırmanın sonucunda katılımcıların kariyer fuarlarını nitelikli işgücüne erişim açısından önemli buldukları, fuarların öğrencilere önemli istihdam olanakları sunabildiği ortaya konulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Bölgesel Kariyer Fuarı, Kuzeydoğu Anadolu Kariyer Fuarı (KUDAKAF), Atatürk Üniversitesi, Algı

1. INTRODUCTION

Career and choice of profession are undoubtedly among the most significant variables influencing a person's life. Making a poor choice at this critical stage would have a negative impact on a person's entire life (Greenhaus and Callanan, 2006). Hence, the time spent in university education stands out as the most decisive period in terms of career and professional choice in this context. Yet, an educational process that focuses solely on teaching professional standards is insufficient to open the door to the successful career individuals expect to have in the future. Especially in the rapidly changing professional life, adapting to the environment and making successful career plans is only possible with an education supported by real-world experience.

From a traditional standpoint, providing students with real-world experiences is possible through various internship programs and applied training. However, regionally organized career fairs nowadays are substantial platforms that offer significant opportunities to bring together both students and recent graduates with employers. In this sense, the Regional Career Fairs (RCFs) organized by the Human Resources Office of the Turkish Presidency (TPHRO) since 2019 under the motto "Talent is Everywhere" stand out as major organizations that provide significant opportunities for students. The RCFs have been held annually under the coordination of TPHRO, hosted by a different university, and in partnership with universities selected by TPHRO in the region. The RCFs aim to bring together public and private sector institutions/organizations with students, thereby facilitating university students' access to job and internship opportunities (Human Resources Office of the Turkish Presidency, n.d.).

This study, in its scope, focused on the KUDAKAF events, organized regionally in Turkey in 2023 and 2025, from the perspective of employer representatives participating in the fair, thereby identifying areas for improvement. Accordingly, the study determined the perceptions of employer representatives towards Atatürk University, its students, and their perceptions towards KUDAKAF through RCFs. Accordingly, the following sections of this article initially provide the subject-related theoretical framework, including a summary of national and international literature, and subsequently present the study materials and methods. Afterward, the latter section reveals the research findings, and the study concludes with a results and discussion section.

2. INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

This section initially presents the concept and significance of career, which forms the basis of this study; subsequently, it discusses the roles of career centers in the career planning process, and career fairs organized under the coordination of TPHRO, based on the relevant literature.

2.1. The Concept of Career and Its Significance

The term "career" can be conceptualized as an individual's gradual and steady advancement in many fields of occupation over the years, gaining experience and skills (Taşlıyan et al, 2011: 233). However, according to another definition, "career" refers to an individual's work history, patterns in professions and job positions, and career advancement both in a profession and in life in general (Greenhaus and Callanan, 2006). All the different definitions of the concept of "career" emphasize that it refers to a process, not a point-specific advancement.

The career development process that needs to be considered in this context refers to all actions undertaken to ensure harmony and development among the roles individuals assume throughout their lives (Güldü and Kart, 2017: 378). Choosing a career is the first step in the career development process. Individuals make career choices at various times and places and are influenced by numerous variables. In this context, four key elements fundamentally influence career choice, including personal interests, self-awareness, personality, and social environment (Wilton, 2011). Guided by these variables, individuals want to choose the field in which they wish to pursue a career, develop themselves, and advance. In other words, individuals experience the career planning process in different contexts, influenced by both individual and societal factors.

Career planning is a process that is the responsibility of both individuals and organizations. Accordingly, an organization must provide opportunities for its employees to enable them to realize their career plans and ensure the necessary knowledge and skill development resources for their career advancement. The most basic approach to accomplish this outcome is to provide opportunities, such as in-company training (Güldü and Kart, 2017: 380). Considering the issue within this framework, university students and recent graduates are highly sensitive to career opportunities, despite their inexperience in career planning. As a result, for

university students and graduates who are still in the early stages of career planning and have not yet entered the profession, any activity that raises awareness about career planning and enables them to establish various connections is of great significance.

2.2. The Role of Career Centers in the Career Planning Process

Nowadays, efforts to recruit qualified personnel to the business world have become widespread, thanks to the competition in higher education resulting from the development of education and training services. The education factor, which influences individual career planning, has become extremely critical in universities. Career development and advisory services, a significant element of education, have also been provided within these institutions, particularly as part of support services (Cevher, 2013: 170).

Career centers, used as a tool for career management, are in-house organizations that provide training and advisory services, facilitating a personal evaluation process. These centers offer counseling services, organize courses, provide opportunities for self-evaluation and career planning, and help them find suitable opportunities. They also organize internal and external training programs and make announcements regarding job openings (Ünver, 2005: 42).

Businesses use several methods in the personnel selection process. These are referred to as insourcing and outsourcing (Akbaba and Günlü, 2011). The method of promoting or transferring individuals already working within the company is called insourcing. However, it is not always possible to meet all personnel needs internally. In such circumstances, outsourcing is resorted to as a method (Şahin, Kafa and Korkmaz, 2021). Collecting resumes, utilizing intermediaries, the Turkish Employment Agency (İŞKUR), the internet, or educational institutions are among the most frequently used methods for outsourcing. Career day events and career fairs, particularly those organized by universities at various times of the year, offer significant opportunities for businesses and institutions to find personnel and for students to find both internships and jobs. Career fairs coordinated by TPHRO are also organized locally by the career centers of universities. These centers, which undertake such a critical task, act as a bridge between employers and students.

Ensuring students benefit from internship opportunities and experience real working life is a crucial aspect that must be emphasized before graduation. Indeed, career fairs offer significant opportunities for both students and graduates. Evaluating career fairs, which provide various presentations, seminars, and interview simulations, in terms of both their effectiveness and participant perception, will contribute to the effectiveness of all future fairs.

2.3. Career Fairs Organized by TPHRO

Career fairs offer students significant advantages, including knowledge about diverse job opportunities, recognition of various sectors, advice on transitioning from school to the workplace, and preparation for networking with professionals (Silkes et al., 2010). Fairs are advantageous for students and participants, revealing vital opportunities for the city and even the public, such as generating new resources, investing in infrastructure like new facilities, and enhancing the social life of the geographical region where they are held (Binbaşıoğlu and Gültekin, 2017).

RCFs are organized in 11 different regions of Türkiye under the coordination of TPHRO and in cooperation with university career centers, with the motto "Talent is Everywhere." These RCFs are organizations that aim to familiarize students continuing their higher education and recent graduates with the real business world, increase their employability, raise awareness about the visibility of sector employers, especially public institutions, and support them in securing the qualified human resources they require.

Career fairs are held nationwide in the Aegean, Thrace, Southern, Central Anatolia, Silk Road, Southeastern, Eastern Anatolia, Northeastern Anatolia, Eastern Black Sea, and Central Black Sea regions. These fairs aim to bring together university students and graduates from public institutions and the private sector, who may propose potential employment opportunities. The Eastern Anatolia Career Fair, initiated in 2019 with the presidential motto "Talent is Everywhere," was held in Erzurum in 2020 and 2022 and later under the name KUDAKAF in 2023 and 2025, hosted by Atatürk University. Surveys conducted among both public and private sector organizations attending the fair measured participants' perceptions regarding career fairs, the organization, and students studying at Atatürk University.

3. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study aimed to measure the perceptions of KUDAKAF visitors regarding career fairs and Atatürk University students and graduates. As hosted by Atatürk University in 2023 and 2025, the study used the visitors of KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 as research material. In line with the study's objective, 220 and 200 employers attending KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25, respectively, participated in the surveys, and 148 and 100 of them completed the forms and responded. The data acquired from all these forms were included in the study and analyzed accordingly. Researchers collected the quantitative data using a Likert-type scale developed specifically for this research during the fair days.

The research design was based on an explanatory case study, and employers participating in KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 comprised the research population. A structured 5-point Likert-type scale was developed for application to the selected sample. The scale consisted of 17 statements to measure employers' past participation in career fairs, their level of satisfaction with KUDAKAF, their perception of Atatürk University students and graduates, and their intention to participate in future fairs (Table 4). The collected quantitative data were analyzed using reliability, frequency, and regression analysis techniques. The following section presents the findings from the analyses.

4. RESULTS

The findings below summarize the analysis results of the data collected from the surveys conducted in this study, which was carried out to measure the perceptions of participants regarding KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25.

4.1. Reliability of Scales

Table 1 presents the reliability test results of the scales used in the study.

Table 1. Reliability Coefficients of Scales

	Cronbach Alpha
KUDAKAF '23	0.848
KUDAKAF '25	0.827

Table 1 indicates that both scales were reliable as their Cronbach's alpha values were greater than 0.70.

4.2. Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 presents data regarding the institutional type of KUDAKAF '23 participants and the cities in which they attended.

Table 2. Information about Institutions Participating in the Study – KUDAKAF '23

Feature		F	%
Participant Profile	Private Sector	61	41.2
	Public Institution	79	53.4
	NGO	8	5.4
City	Erzurum	103	69.6
	Ankara	17	11.5
	İstanbul	8	5.4
	Ağrı	7	4.7
	Bayburt	3	2.0
	Artvin	3	2.0
	Erzincan	2	1.4
	Kars	2	1.4
	Ardahan	1	0.7
	İzmir	1	0.7
	Mersin	1	0.7

According to Table 2, 41.2%, 53.4%, and 5.4% of the participants were from private institutions, public sectors, and NGOs, respectively. Additionally, 69.6% of the participants were from Erzurum, with attendees from a total of 11 cities. This finding is significant in terms of expanding the scope of the fair beyond a single community.

Table 3 lists data on the institutional type of KUDAKAF '25 visitors and the cities in which they attended.

Table 3. Information about Institutions Participating in the Study – KUDAKAF '25

Feature		F	%
Participant Profile	Private Sector	40	40.0
	Public Institution	60	60.0
City	Erzurum	75	75.0
	Ankara	8	8.0
	İstanbul	9	9.0
	Artvin	2	2.0
	Ardahan	2	2.0
	Bayburt	1	1.0
	Antalya	1	1.0
	Kars	1	1.0
	Bingöl	1	1.0

As listed in Table 3, about 40% and 60% of the participants were from private and public institutions, respectively. Additionally, 75% of the participants were from Erzurum province, with attendees from a total of 9 cities. This finding is also valuable in terms of broadening the participant profile of the fair.

Table 4 presents the statistical data on the questions asked to KUDAKAF '23 participants in the survey and their responses.

Table 4. Survey Questions and Frequencies – KUDAKAF '23

Questions	1		2		3		4		5	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. We have previously attended career fairs held in Türkiye	19	12.8	5	3.4	7	4.7	50	33.8	67	45.3
2. We have previously attended in career fairs held in Erzurum	31	20.9	10	6.8	6	4.1	37	25.0	64	43.2
3. We have previously provided internship opportunities to students we contacted through career fairs	30	20.3	24	16.2	20	13.5	34	23.0	40	27.0
4. We have previously employed students we contacted through career fairs	34	23.0	23	15.5	31	20.9	32	21.6	28	18.9
5. We find career fairs useful	2	1.4	3	2.0	4	2.7	44	29.7	95	64.2
6. We believe that career centers play a critical role in organizing such fairs	2	1.4	3	2.0	5	3.4	45	30.4	93	62.8
7. We found the KUDAKAF '23 fair organization generally successful	7	4.7	13	8.8	19	12.8	51	34.5	58	39.2
8. KUDAKAF '23 provided visitors with all the necessary support during the registration and preparation process	10	6.8	11	7.4	18	12.2	48	32.4	61	41.2
9. We believe that the promotional activities before KUDAKAF '23 were sufficient	3	2.0	13	8.8	24	16.2	47	31.8	61	41.2
10. Our institution considered the number and profile of visitors who attended KUDAKAF '23 satisfactory	3	2.0	9	6.1	20	13.5	51	34.5	65	43.9
11. We consider re-attending this fair next year	5	3.4	4	2.7	13	8.8	52	35.1	74	50.0
12. We attended this fair voluntarily	5	3.4	1	.7	8	5.4	50	33.8	84	56.8
13. We have sufficient information about Atatürk University	-	-	3	2.0	11	7.4	51	34.5	83	56.1
14. We have a favorable perception of Atatürk University students	1	0.7	-	-	9	6.1	59	39.9	79	53.1
15. We have previously provided internship opportunities to Atatürk University students	23	15.5	18	12.2	29	19.6	32	21.6	46	31.1
16. We have previously employed graduates from Atatürk University	13	8.8	13	8.8	20	13.5	43	29.1	59	39.9
17. We would like to employ Atatürk University graduates	2	1.4	2	1.4	7	4.7	50	33.8	87	58.8

Accordingly, the following are the analysis results regarding the statements made by the participants in KUDAKAF '23.

Analysis of responses to the statement, "**We have previously attended career fairs held in Türkiye,**" demonstrated that 79.1% of participants responded positively, indicating that a sizable portion of visitors had fair experience in the past. For the statement, "**We have previously attended career fairs held in Erzurum?**" about 68.2% of the visitors responded favorably. This data also revealed that most visitors had a fair experience in Erzurum.

Regarding the responses to the statement, "**We have previously provided internship opportunities to students we contacted through career fairs,**" almost 50% of participants expressed that they had provided internships to students through fairs. Given that half of the companies provided such a response, career fairs explicitly provide significant internship opportunities. Analysis of the responses to the statement, "**We previously employed students we contacted through career fairs,**" revealed that 40.5%, a considerably high rate, of visitors employed students through fairs, convincing the significance of career fairs.

Considering the responses to the statement, **"We find career fairs useful?"** 64.2% and 29.7% of participants responded "definitely agree" and "agree", respectively. Similarly, analysis of the responses to the statement, **"We believe that career centers play a critical role in organizing such fairs,"** revealed that 62.8% and 30.4% of visitors responded "definitely agree" and "agree", respectively. These data explicitly indicate that the perception of career centers is quite positive.

Regarding the responses to the statement, **"We found the KUDAKAF '23 fair organization generally successful,"** 39.2% and 34.5% of participants responded "definitely agree" and "agree", respectively. Concerning the statement, **"KUDAKAF '23 provided visitors with all the necessary support during the registration and preparation process,"** while 41.2% of participants responded "definitely agree," 32.4% answered "agree."

Analysis of the responses to the statement, **"We believe that the promotional activities before KUDAKAF '23 were sufficient?"** demonstrated that 41.2% and 31.8% of visitors responded "strongly agree" and "agree," respectively. Hence, this data suggests that career fairs should emphasize more promotional activities. Regarding the responses to the statement, **"Our institution considered the number and profile of visitors who attended KUDAKAF '23 satisfactory,"** 43.9% of visitors stated "strongly agree," whereas 34.5% expressed "agree."

Considering the responses to the statement, **"We consider re-attending this fair next year,"** almost 50.0% and 35.1% of participants responded "definitely agree" and "agree." This result is explicitly significant in emphasizing the effectiveness of the career fairs. Analysis of the responses to the statement **"We attended this fair voluntarily"** revealed that 56.8% and 33.8% of participants stated "definitely agree" and "agree," respectively.

Analysis of the responses to the statement **"We have sufficient information about Atatürk University"** revealed that 56.1% of visitors responded "strongly agree," and 34.5% answered "agree." This data explicitly highlights the need for the university to place more emphasis on its promotional activities, particularly during fair seasons. Considering the responses to the statement, **"We have a favorable perception of Atatürk University students,"** 52.4% and 39.9% of visitors responded "strongly agree" and "agree," respectively.

Analysis of the responses to the statement, **"We have previously provided internship opportunities to Atatürk University students,"** revealed that 52.7% of participants had provided internship opportunities; however, 27.7% indicated the contrary. Regarding the statement, **"We have previously employed Atatürk University graduates,"** while 69% of participants responded that they provided employment opportunities to graduates, 17.6% disagreed. Finally, analysis of the responses to the statement **"We would like to employ Atatürk University graduates"** revealed that 92.6% of visitors had a positive view on this issue. As a result, it is reasonable to indicate that career fairs reinforce positive perceptions of universities and their graduates.

Table 5 presents the statistical data on the questions asked to the KUDAKAF '25 visitors and their answers in the survey.

Table 5. Survey Questions and Frequencies – KUDAKAF '25

Question	1		2		3		4		5	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%
1. We have previously attended career fairs held in Türkiye	9	9.0	4	4.0	4	4.0	27	27.0	56	56.0
2. We have previously attended in career fairs held in Erzurum	18	18.0	9	9.0	2	2.0	15	15.0	56	56.0
3. We have previously provided internship opportunities to students we contacted through career fairs	18	18.0	14	14.0	10	10.0	27	27.0	31	31.0
4. We have previously employed students we contacted through career fairs	16	16.0	16	16.0	23	23.0	17	17.0	28	28.0
5. We find career fairs useful	3	3.0	1	1.0	9	9.0	22	22.0	65	65.0
6. We believe that career centers play a critical role in organizing such fairs	1	1.0	3	3.0	9	9.0	25	25.0	62	62.0
7. We found the KUDAKAF '25 fair organization generally successful	4	4.0	-		22	22.0	34	34.0	40	40.0
8. KUDAKAF '25 provided visitors with all the necessary support during the registration and preparation process	3	3.0	3	3.0	18	18.0	38	38.0	38	38.0
9. We believe that the promotional activities before KUDAKAF '25 were sufficient	7	7.0	7	7.0	19	19.0	34	34.0	33	33.0
10. Our institution considered the number and profile of visitors who attended KUDAKAF '25 satisfactory	7	7.0	3	3.0	11	11.0	34	34.0	45	45.0
11. We consider re-attending this fair next year	2	2.0	2	2.0	11	11.0	32	32.0	53	53.0
12. We attended this fair voluntarily	2	2.0	2	2.0	15	15.0	33	33.0	48	48.0
13. We have sufficient information about Atatürk University	3	3.0	3	3.0	7	7.0	28	28.0	59	59.0
14. We have a favorable perception of Atatürk University students	1	1.0	2	2.0	6	6.0	32	32.0	59	59.0
15. We have previously provided internship opportunities to Atatürk University students	13	13.0	12	12.0	13	13.0	28	28.0	34	34.0
16. We have previously employed graduates from Atatürk University	9	9.0	10	10.0	14	14.0	29	29.0	38	38.0
17. We would like to employ Atatürk University graduates	3	3.0	1	1.0	11	11.0	32	32.0	53	53.0

Below are the analysis results regarding the statements made by the participants in the KUDAKAF '25. Accordingly, analysis of the responses to the statement, **"We have previously attended career fairs held in Türkiye,"** revealed that 83% of participants had already attended a career fair, indicating that a sizable portion of participants had experience with fairs. Similarly, analysis of the responses to the question **"We have previously attended career fairs held in Erzurum"** demonstrated that 71% of the participants attended past fairs in this province. This data also proves that a significant majority of participants had experience with fairs held in Erzurum province.

Regarding the responses to the statement, **"We have previously provided internship opportunities to students you contacted through career fairs,"** 58% of participants indicated they had provided internships to students through past fairs. Thus, over half of the companies confirmed that career fairs provided substantial internship opportunities. Similarly, for the statement, **"We have previously employed students contacted through career fairs,"** 45% of participants responded that they employed students through past career fairs. This figure is also significant, as it indicates the criticalness of career fairs.

Considering the responses to the statement, **"We found career fairs useful,"** 65% and 22% of participants expressed "definitely agree" and "agree," respectively. Correspondingly, the responses to the statement, **"We believe that career centers play a critical role in organizing such fairs,"** revealed that 62% and 25% of participants responded "definitely agree" and "agree," indicating a significantly positive perception of career centers.

Regarding the responses to the statement, **"We found the KUDAKAF '25 fair organization generally successful,"** 40% and 34% of participants expressed "definitely agree" and "agree," respectively; however, 22% responded "undecided." For the statement, **"KUDAKAF '25 provided visitors with all the necessary support during the registration and preparation process,"** 38% and 38% of participants responded "definitely agree" and "agree," respectively.

Analysis of the responses to the statement, **"We believe the promotional activities before KUDAKAF '25 were sufficient,"** revealed that 33% and 34% of the participants responded "strongly agree" and "agree," whereas 19% of them were "undecided." Accordingly, this data hints that additional promotional activities are necessary for career fairs. Regarding the responses to the statement, **"Our institution considered the number and profile of visitors who attended KUDAKAF '25 satisfactory,"** 45% and 34% of the participants reported "strongly agree" and "agree," respectively.

For the responses to the statement, **"We consider re-attending this fair next year,"** the study found that 53% and 32% of the participants responded "definitely agree" and "agree," respectively. Hence, a significant majority of the visitors acknowledged the effectiveness of the fair. Similarly, for the responses to the statement, **"We participated in this fair voluntarily,"** 48% and 33% of the participants indicated "definitely agree" and "agree," respectively.

Considering the responses to the statement, **"We have sufficient information about Atatürk University,"** 59% and 28% of the participants responded "strongly agree" and "agree," respectively. Similarly, for the responses to the statement, **"We have a favorable perception of Atatürk University students,"** a sizable portion of participants responded positively; 59% "strongly agree" and 32% "agree," respectively.

Finally, analysis of the responses to the statement, **"We have previously provided internship opportunities to Atatürk University students,"** revealed that while 62% of participants had provided internship opportunities, 25% of them had provided no internship opportunities. Regarding the statement, **"We previously employed Atatürk University graduates,"** 67% of participants had provided employment opportunities to graduates, whereas 19% disagreed. Finally, for the responses to the statement, **"We would like to employ Atatürk University graduates,"** 85% of respondents expressed a positive view on this matter. As a result, it is reasonable to interpret this data as an indicator that career fairs promote positive opinions of universities and their graduates.

Table 6 presents the regression analysis results to measure the effect of participants' satisfaction levels with KUDAKAF '23 on their intention to re-attend career fairs.

Table 6. The Effect of Satisfaction Levels on Re-attending Intention (KUDAKAF '23)

Dependent Variable (Re-attending intention)	Independent Variable (Satisfaction level)		
	B	t	p
	0.439	7.288	0.000
R ²	0.267		
Adjusted R ²	0.262		
F	53.121		

Also, Table 7 shows the regression analysis results to measure the effect of participants' satisfaction levels with KUDAKAF '25 on their intention to re-attend career fairs.

Table 7. The Effect of Satisfaction Levels on Re-attending Intention (KUDAKAF '25)

Dependent Variable (Re-attending intention)	Independent Variable (Satisfaction level)		
	B	t	p
	0.349	4.145	0.000
R ²	0.149		
Adjusted R ²	0.140		
F	17.177		

Analysis of the study results revealed that satisfaction levels for both fairs have a significant and positive effect on the re-attending intention to career fairs. Considering that career fairs are regularly held events, satisfaction derived from attending any given fair will likely foster a desire to re-attend future fairs held in the same or different regions. As a result, it is reasonable to conclude that such a favorable cycle explicitly emphasizes the significance of any successfully completed fair.

4.3. KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 Comparison

Career fairs are annual events that are regularly held. Hence, satisfaction with attending a fair promotes re-attending future fairs held either in the same or different regions, and this positive cycle highlights the significance of completing each fair successfully. Thanks to the experience-enhancing contributions of RCFs, participant satisfaction is expected to rise annually rather than decline. Comparing KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 will substantially shed light on this topic.

Analysis of the responses to the statement, "**We have previously attended career fairs held in Türkiye,**" revealed that KUDAKAF '25 participants had more fair experience (83%) than KUDAKAF '23 participants (79.1%). This data indicates that KUDAKAF '25 was more successful in making career fairs more widespread throughout Türkiye and in reaching out to institutions and companies with fair experience during the fair preparation process.

Regarding the responses to the statement, "**We have previously attended career fairs held in Erzurum,**" the present study found that KUDAKAF '25 participants (71%) displayed higher attendance at career fairs held in Erzurum compared to KUDAKAF '23 participants (68.1%). Career fairs are held annually; as a result, this rate is expected to increase with each fair.

About the responses to the statement, "**We have previously provided internship opportunities to students we contacted through career fairs,**" the study found that KUDAKAF '25 participants (58%) reported providing more internship opportunities than KUDAKAF '23 participants (50%). This data explicitly indicates the increasing significance of the relationship established between students attending career fairs and employers. The study also identified similar rates for the responses to the statement, "**We have previously employed students we contacted through career fairs.**" Accordingly, KUDAKAF '25 participants (45%) reportedly provided more employment opportunities than KUDAKAF '23 participants (40.5%), indicating the significance of career fairs for students' and graduates' employment, a widely recognized issue every year.

Analysis of the responses to the statement, "**We find career fairs useful,**" revealed that more KUDAKAF '23 participants (93.9%) found the fairs useful than KUDAKAF '25 participants (87%). Such an opposite finding may not be unique to KUDAKAF; rather, it might be an outcome of experience with all career fairs. However, a general assessment of KUDAKAF '25 is also necessary to identify potential imperfections for further improvement. For the responses to the statement, "**We believe that career centers play a critical role in organizing such fairs,**" the study determined that more KUDAKAF '23 participants (93.2%) were aware of career centers than KUDAKAF '25 participants (87%). The primary reason for this outcome might be that career fairs, which directly manage a career fair through a rigorous, months-long, intense

organizational process, may also find it difficult to simultaneously advertise themselves during this process. As a result, it is necessary to project diverse activities to make the career centers more visible.

Considering the responses to the statement, "**We found the KUDAKAF fair organization generally successful,**" an almost equal number of participants in KUDAKAF '25 (74%) and KUDAKAF '23 (73.7%) reported that the fairs were successful. The fact that the fair's rating remained consistently high demonstrates the organization's perceived success. For the responses to the statement, "**KUDAKAF '25 provided visitors with all the necessary support during the registration and preparation process,**" more KUDAKAF '25 participants (76%) reported their satisfaction compared to KUDAKAF '23 participants (73.6%). This data also indicates increasing experience of organizers with the fair registration and preparation processes.

In response to the statement, "**We believe that the promotional activities before KUDAKAF '25 were sufficient,**" more KUDAKAF '23 participants (73%) found the promotional activities sufficient than KUDAKAF '25 participants (67%). These results, which demonstrate the significance of maintaining a high level of awareness regarding the fair, suggest that more comprehensive promotional activities could be designed accordingly.

Analysis of the responses to the statement, "**Our institution considered the number and profile of visitors who attended KUDAKAF '25 satisfactory,**" revealed that KUDAKAF '25 (79%) and KUDAKAF '23 participants (78.4%) expressed satisfaction at almost equal levels. Hence, it is a positive outcome that a standard has been established regarding visitor numbers and profiles. The study also found a similar result for the responses to the statement, "**We consider re-attending this fair next year.**" Indeed, both KUDAKAF '25 (85%) and KUDAKAF '23 participants (85.1%) reported a high level of similar intention for re-attending future fairs. As a result, maintaining an overall standard of fair success is also a highly gratifying finding for the university.

Regarding the responses to the statement, "**We have sufficient information about Atatürk University,**" the study found that KUDAKAF '23 participants (90.6%) were more knowledgeable than KUDAKAF '25 participants (87%). This data indicates that Atatürk University should advertise itself more intensively, both before and during the fair, especially to companies and institutions attending from outside the Erzurum province. In response to the statement, "**We have a favorable perception of Atatürk University students,**" both KUDAKAF '25 (91%) and KUDAKAF '23 participants (92.3%) expressed highly similar and positive perception rates. This data is also significant in terms of how fairs strengthen students' perceptions.

Analysis of the responses to the statement, "**We have previously employed graduates from Atatürk University,**" revealed that KUDAKAF '23 participants (69%) employed more graduates than KUDAKAF '25 participants (67%). Similarly, in response to the statement, "**We would like to employ Atatürk University graduates,**" KUDAKAF '23 participants (92.6%) reported a higher intention to employ graduates than KUDAKAF '25 participants (85%). Although employment aspirations remain high at KUDAKAF '25, the lower employment intention compared to 2023 suggests that KUDAKAF '23 participants may have employed Atatürk University graduates more frequently and had more positive experiences with them.

5. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to measure the perceptions of companies and institutions attending KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 regarding career fairs and compare the results of the two fairs. The study performed surveys on the days of the fairs, targeting representatives of the private sector and public institutions. While study participants were completely voluntary, the study adhered to the necessary ethical guidelines throughout the research process.

Career fairs are crucial both for helping students adapt to changing environmental conditions and for fostering positive competition among employers (Silkes et al., 2010). Universities, and especially career centers, are aware of this significance when organizing regional career fairs.

The continuously evolving fair experience and accumulating institutional memory raise expectations that each career fair should be more effective and successful than the last one, while also motivating organizers to put in even more effort. As a result, the present study findings reveal that KUDAKAF '25 was equally successful in some aspects and even more successful in others than KUDAKAF '23; hence, they serve as inspiration to put in more effort for future fairs.

The study findings reveal that the vast majority of participants have experience with fairs in Erzurum, and a significant portion of the participants employ students and/or graduates through these fairs. This data also highlights the essence of career fairs in meeting the demands of both institutions that seek a qualified workforce and students and graduates who aspire to access employment opportunities. As a result, these findings are consistent with studies reporting that career fairs significantly increase employability (Kolodinsky et al., 2006).

In light of the study results, it is reasonable to conclude that a sizable portion of participants had a very favorable perception of fairs and career centers. These results are also motivational for career centers, which play a critical role in organizing career fairs. Regarding participants' satisfaction levels, this study, like others in the literature, reveals similarities with findings indicating that companies and institutions that had the opportunity to promote themselves profited substantially from the fairs and were content (Şengel et al., 2018).

The positive responses to questions about providing internship opportunities to students contacted through the fairs and offering employment opportunities for Atatürk University graduates also indicate that career fairs are an effective activity in line with their purpose, creating substantial opportunities to reach a broader range of participants. Participant responses, in line with the aims of the fairs, reveal that career fairs are important and fruitful, particularly for institutions attending from different provinces, in acquiring knowledge about host and partner universities, getting acquainted with students, and even recruiting students/graduates to their talent pools through applications such as interview simulations.

The overwhelmingly favorable responses to the statement, "We would like to employ Atatürk University graduates," are also a significant indicator of the fair's success in introducing the university and its students to institutions. As a result, all this data validates the significance of career fairs, the crucial role of career centers in organizing such fairs, and the opportunities they provide for a win-win situation for both employers and students.

In conclusion, this study contributes to the relevant literature due to its originality, as it is the only study focusing on the KUDAKAF '23 and KUDAKAF '25 examples. However, the fact that the study only surveyed employers can be considered a limitation, and future studies on the fairs could also include participating students or graduates in their analyses.

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